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D2.2 Pre-piloting technological readiness

Design requirements for a data sharing architecture

Authors

Danny Lämmerhirt [WAAG]

Pourya Omid [WAGG]

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Executive Summary

This document describes the conceptual and architectural framework as well as a development plan for EXCENTRIC pilot organisations on how to share data internally and with their network. To guide the technological development, we draw on three theoretical concepts: data intermediaries, data infrastructure and platform core/periphery. These concepts inform the design of a **core infrastructure** as a common denominator for all the pilots and the pilot-specific applications which are specific to pilots. In addition, we explain how we intend to apply value-sensitive design as the central design approach to introduce moral reflection into the technology development process and to shape the technology based on values that are important for the Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries (CCSI).

In section 1, we define concepts guiding our design work: data intermediaries, data infrastructure and platform core/periphery. Each concept focuses on a different aspect of the question how data is made useful when it circulates across locally specific contexts. We conclude this chapter with an outline of the elements of data intermediaries we are planning to design, build, and test in the project and provide an overview of the Solid framework, which we will use to design the data sharing architecture for EXCENTRIC.

Section 2 explains how we apply value-sensitive design (VSD) as a design-based research methodology in combination with agile development processes. The chapter explains how we apply VSD to conceptualise values (identifying stakeholders and values), how we empirically study them (eliciting values and norms from pilots through methods like prototyping and user testing) and how we translate values into technology (translating values design specifications). The contours of the VSD methodology are accompanied by a technology development plan which describes iterative phases of technology development. As presented in the EXCENTRIC proposal, the project uses the Solid protocol to enable data sharing. We describe how Solid and data Pods will be used for the purpose of data sharing. We cover the following Solid standard components: data Pods (organizational storage spaces), applications/services (peripheral elements), and identity and access control and standard data models.

Section 3 concludes this report with an overview list of the first design requirements. This list acts as a living document for the iterative process of technology development. As the project progresses and pilot technologies are further developed in the second year, the list of design requirements and underlying values will grow and be further specified. This is in part because our VSD approach elicits values and norms regarding the design context of the pilot projects, which require further definition and iteration during the co-creation workshops planned for Q1 '26 with the pilot organisations.

1. Data innovation and data sharing in CCSI

This chapter provides a conceptual description of EXCENTRIC's data sharing architecture for inter-organisational data sharing. The chapter details the components of this architecture and outlines relevant questions for its design, development, and implementation.

The EXCENTRIC project supports the digital transition aimed at sustainable and responsible growth in the European Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries (CCSI). The overall project goal is to foster the organizations' utilization of data in their daily operations and to develop and implement a collaborative data practice in six pilots under real working conditions to allow for effective integration of data into daily operations. To do so, the project aims to develop three aspects of data sharing architecture to different technology readiness levels (TRLs), namely data sharing mechanisms and practices (TRL 7), decentralized data management (TRL 6), and analytics applications (TRL 6). The resulting data sharing architecture is aimed to provide core functionalities for inter-organisational data sharing, as well as organisation-specific functionalities.

Data is often seen as a resource that can be made interoperable and reusable across contexts. But data sharing and reuse require the right means: hardware to house data, instruments to manipulate data, standard data models that are flexible enough to meet different pragmatic needs, practices of working with data, and rules for what can be done with data, to name a but a few (Leonelli and Tempini 2020). Technologies and practices for circulating data are also expressions of different values. One may think of the sharing of person-related data which is bound to consent, and which may require aggregating data so as to hide personally-identifiable information. At the same time, too highly aggregated data may not serve the analytical needs of an organisation wanting to reuse such data. Data sharing architectures are therefore manifestations of values: What is worthwhile knowing about the world and how should it be put into categories, in whose benefit? Who should have access to what kinds of data, based on what grounds? What kinds of reuse should be enabled, and which ones should be constrained or entirely forbidden? The answers to such questions can be found in values, that is conceptions of what is important and desirable, which guide individuals' and organizations' decisions and actions across contexts.

Any design of data sharing architecture has to address these values. One way of doing so is by understanding how data sharing architecture may promote certain values through their its design. In the following, we provide three theoretical lenses on data

sharing architecture. Each lens draws our attention to different aspects of data sharing architecture which are important to consider for its design and development process.

1.1 Definitions

To guide our design work, we draw on the following theoretical concepts: data intermediaries, data infrastructure and platform core/periphery. The concept of **data intermediaries** us unpack the question of how data, coming from a producer or source, can be transformed to be usable, useful, and valuable for a reuser and how interests are negotiated by an intermediary. The concept of **platform core and periphery** helps to make clear what parts of a data intermediary provide foundational services that affect an entire ecosystem of actors, and what parts are peripheral elements that can be built on top of a platform core. This lens is relevant to understand so-called technological value levers, that is foundational core components that manifest certain values and impact a wide range of actors. Lastly, the concept of **data infrastructure** is helpful to unpack how information systems are made meaningful in everyday organizational practices and the role of standardisation for plugging these systems into existing socio-technical infrastructures. When is a standardised information system practically useful in specific organisational contexts, as well as across organisations? How does an information system will be adapted into existing technical systems, standards, rules and practices?

In summary, these three concepts enable us to point out different research questions for our design work that highlight what needs to be built within EXCENTRIC, and how the developed tools should be tested. We conclude this section (section 1.2) with a list of research questions that point out specific design challenges relevant for the EXCENTRIC pilots.

1.1.1 Data sharing architecture as data intermediary

In order for data to travel, several conditions must usually be met. For instance, it must be clear what rights of reuse apply, and data must be in a form that is amenable for reuse. One concept to unpack mechanisms facilitating data reuse is the notion of the data intermediary. Data intermediaries are defined as entities that operate in between data producers and data consumers and broker interests between these parties, usually by legal and technical means (Janssen and Singh 2022).

Examples of data intermediaries include open databases, personal information management systems, specific organisational forms like data cooperatives, and data trusts (ibid). Literature shows that data intermediaries can take many shapes and that there is no one-size-fits all solution to designing them. Some research into data intermediaries stresses their role as rights management frameworks for data, providing data access. Other research considers how data intermediaries format and transform data to make it fit the knowledge needs and abilities of reusers. Data intermediaries can take many forms and provide different functions, depending on what data is processed (personal, non-personal), whether data will be stored in an archive for later

research or provided as real-time data streams, and whether data is open or not.

Since data intermediaries take different shapes and provide different functions, recent research has therefore proposed to think of data intermediaries in component parts and design patterns that can be assembled to fit the needs of specific needs stakeholders (see section 1.2 for a comprehensive overview of these component parts). Within the EXCENTRIC project, we organise the development of a data sharing architecture along these component parts. In addition, we are considering how these component parts must be designed to gather data from a data source/producer, and to make this data accessible to reusers.

1.1.2 Data sharing architecture as data infrastructure

EXCENTRIC's goal is to develop a data sharing architecture to circulate and reuse operational data across organisations. Paraphrasing Science and Technology Studies (STS), the project wants to build a data sharing architecture which can grow into a data *infrastructure* (Star and Ruhleder 1996), that is a set of technologies and practices that span multiple organisations and contexts for reusing operational data.

The field of STS, and the sociology of information infrastructure (Bowker and Star 1999) in particular remind us that an infrastructure is never merely a set of technologies that can be designed *de novo*. Rather, infrastructures are technologies that are learnt and enacted through practice, which grow out of existing legacy technologies and practices, and which must be able to span multiple situations and local contexts by setting standards for work (they are large-scale). These standards are usually subject to technical, social, political, and ethical debates before the infrastructure can be taken for granted in routine use.

For the EXCENTRIC project this means that standard models for datasets and sharing must be developed open-ended enough to meet the needs of different organisations. At the same time, the EXCENTRIC project has to consider how these standards for data sharing can be implemented within existing routine work procedures and legacy technologies. In the logic of infrastructure studies, a data sharing architecture is not simply designed, but must evolve in relation to existing systems (Star and Ruhleder 1996). Within EXCENTRIC, we employ the concept of data infrastructure primarily to guide our development of technology components, and to test how these resonate with daily work practices and other existing technologies of pilot organisations.

1.1.3 Data sharing architecture as platform core/periphery

EXCENTRIC plans to develop a decentralised data sharing architecture which can form the basis for a larger ecosystem for data sharing and reuse. Data sharing commonly raises questions of who has access to data and who can determine what data can be shared and used. The study of digital platforms has shown that some component parts of a data sharing architecture are particularly influential to determine what data can

be shared and reused, under what conditions. Acknowledging that the term platform has many meanings (Gillespie 2010), we draw on engineering perspectives (Gawer 2014) and political economic understandings of platforms (Van Dijk 2020) to conceptualise crucial components to develop.

We define a platform as a software-based system that is built on a modular and extensible codebase. The codebase of a platform provides core functionalities and additional functionalities for users through peripheral applications that interoperate with the core platform (Tiwana et al., 2010). The distinction between platform core and periphery helps to identify which components and functions of a data sharing architecture should be more infrastructurally embedded in a data sharing architecture and will apply to the entire ecosystem (the core), and which functionalities can be added by third-parties and be usable by parts of the ecosystem (peripheral elements used by selected organisations). Another reason to adopt core/periphery thinking is that it enables us to theorise the distribution of power by means of data sharing and reuse are coordinated and regulated, and the instillment of values into the coordination of a data sharing ecosystem.

Platform studies argue that the primary role of a platform provider is to facilitate ecosystems and interactions across users, other platform providers, and third parties. To coordinate these actors, platforms use “boundary resources” (Ghazawneh & Henfridsson, 2010). Boundary resources are platform core functionalities to enable external developers to contribute to the ecosystem. An example would be Twitter’s open application programming interface (API) which has provided the basis for many third-party apps. Other examples include software development kits (SDK), legal guidelines and terms of service, identity management software, as well as application approval processes (Jacobs et al. 2021).

Boundary resources are therefore control mechanisms for ecosystems and crucial “socio-technical manifestations of the platform provider’s power to influence a platform ecosystem” (Jacobs et al 2021). They are also important to theorise the power to enforce values within a data sharing architecture. They are the means by which developers “assert their ideas of conceptions, weighings, and operationalisations of values” (Greene and Shilton 2018) to the core platform as well as the peripheral ecosystem.

The core functionalities, or boundary resources, of EXCENTRIC’s data sharing architecture are therefore of key importance for value-sensitive design (Jacobs et al. 2021) that contributes to the enforcement of shared norms and the realization of different forms of value for different organisations. By conceiving EXCENTRIC’s data sharing architecture as a mix of core and peripheral functions, we can develop a clearer understanding of which functionalities need to be designed to serve a broad set of stakeholders in the cultural and creative industries, and which functionalities are use-case or organisation-specific functionalities.

1.2 Designing data sharing architecture

In this section, we describe how the three definitions provided above influence our vision for a data sharing architecture. We will draw together how we plan to use the three perspectives to inform our development process. Afterwards, we will present how these perspectives map onto pilot projects (section 1.2.1) and how we will apply this lens to the development of an architecture based on the Solid protocol.

The perspectives of data intermediaries, data infrastructure, and platform core/periphery raise different questions on what influences the reuse of data beyond one context. Here we want to draw these perspectives together:

- **Data intermediary perspective:** What component parts are needed to transport data and make it reusable for a user while taking into account the interests of other stakeholders producing and managing data? How does an upstream data production stage impact the downstream data reuse?
- **Data infrastructure perspective:** How should a standard for datasets and data sharing processes look like to be applicable across organisations while satisfying their needs in the context of their daily organisational operations? What legacy technologies and practices exist across organisations and how do they influence the adoption of a novel data sharing architecture?
- **Platform core/periphery perspective:** What component parts shall provide core functionalities for all actors, and what parts shall provide peripheral functionalities to coordinate data sharing across pilot organisations and their networks? What values should guide the design of core functionalities to arrive at desirable ecosystem interactions, as well as reuse of data that is beneficial for the stakeholders involved?

In sum, the data intermediary perspective addresses what components make data flow from a producer to reusers, while an infrastructure perspective looks at the tension between developing standards for data sharing and locally¹ situated needs for data. The platform lens looks at which components of our data sharing architecture have wide-ranging effects on other actors.

Figure 1 provides an overview of characteristic components and services of a data intermediary. We will draw from this analysis to select the specific components and services that we will develop further in the development plan for EXCENTRIC. Figure 1 is the result of a comparative study (Schweihoff et al. 2024) of data intermediation services which aimed to identify defining characteristics of data intermediary services that can be used to distinguish them based on their services and data practices.

Figure 1 : Overview of components & characteristics of data intermediaries (Schweihoff et al. 2024)

Figure 1 is useful for our purposes because it highlights different component parts of data sharing architecture. Within EXCENTRIC, we plan to build certain components as an infrastructural standard function for all (future) actors using the architecture, including data access management, while also managing third-party peripheral elements (e. g. data consumer apps) and relationships between data producers and reusers.

Within EXCENTRIC, we plan to build architecture that provides expandable core functionalities for all pilot organisations and their networks, as well as peripheral functionalities. While we develop specific core functionalities to support pilot projects, we also want to keep it expandable over time, for example by including possibilities to add novel standard datasets, novel data sharing rules, or other standards. This core is also expandable for analytics services, that is third-party apps which enable using data in specific ways: e. g. for trend analysis of ticket sales, audience profiling, marketing sales, or other purposes. To make the data sharing architecture expandable in the future, we follow the argument that it is important to build the infrastructural core and its peripheral elements as separate components and to enable interoperability between them.

1.2.1 Technical components of data sharing architecture

Here, we provide an overview of the technical components that EXCENTRIC's data sharing architecture needs to incorporate. This list is based on initial interviews and workshops with partner organisations (see D 2.1) as well as a literature review on defining characteristics of data intermediaries (Schweihoff et al. 2024).

We consider some of these elements as core elements, while others are peripheral elements. We identify the core elements based on their crucial role for facilitating data sharing between databases and analytics applications. The separation between analytics and hosting is a key principle for decentralised data architectures, making hosting and analytics exchangeable components. On the other hand, standardised data models, identity management and access controls, and computational interfaces for data collection and transformation are core functions because they enable decentralised databases and analytics apps to speak to one another.

In summary, **core elements** include:

- **Standard data models:** This includes datasets that are reusable by other organisations by using shared data types, terminology, data formats/structures, and data fields.
- **Identity management and access control:** This includes services for user authentication and authorization, such as through bespoke consent systems or standards like O.Auth 2.0. It also includes management of usage policies, access rights (e. g. READ, WRITE queries) and the management of third-party apps that can be built on top of a data intermediary.
- **Data collection and transformation interfaces:** This includes functionalities to import data from third-party data sources into a core data sharing architecture.

Peripheral elements include:

- **Data hosting:** This includes services for storage, access, and data availability to consumers (such as hosting). Data intermediaries can make use of personal data stores for person-related data, or other (decentralised) databases.
- **Analytics:** This includes mechanisms to enable data reuse, including managing algorithms that can be run on the data but require specific consent.

In EXCENTRIC the **Solid protocol** is used as the supporting open standard specification to enable data sharing. Solid enables interoperability by employing linked data and shared vocabularies such as Schema.org. This shared vocabulary provides a universal meaning of data which for instance allows applications to (re)use data for the creation of new services. In contrast to how current platforms and data in the current web are coupled in silos, the overarching goal of Solid is to decouple data from

platforms and provide affordances for decentralised web applications for information exchange in a secure and privacy respecting way (Figure 2). The Solid standard covers the following three key components:(1) **data Pods** (storage), (2) **identity management and access control**, and (3) **standard data models**.

Data Pods

A Solid Pod acts as a user's data space on the web, capable of storing various types of data. The Solid ecosystem² aims to provide a place where data, interactions, and media can be stored, shared, and managed by the owner of the data in a portable way. The pilot organisations and their network in EXCENTRIC will each have their own Solid Pod.

Figure 2: A depiction of the exchange of decoupled data between (organisational data pods) and applications (apps)

Identity and Access Control

Identity within Solid is handled via decentralised identity, specifically using WebID³ and Solid-OIDC⁴. The Solid-OIDC specification is built upon the widely adopted standards of OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect. OAuth 2.0 is the underlying authorisation framework that allows a third-party application to obtain limited access to an HTTP service, either on behalf of a resource owner or on its own behalf, without sharing user credentials directly. Users maintain control by managing access (read/write permissions) for applications, other people, or agents, and by determining how and under which conditions data is shared. Access control is managed using Web Access Control (WAC)⁵ and Access Control Policy (ACP)⁶ specifications. Solid specification

requires the implementation of either one or both on the server-side⁷.

Standard data models

Within the EXCENTRIC project, we aim to develop datasets that are reusable across pilot organisations, developing standards for the following data types, including a standard terminology, data fields, and data formats:

- Transaction data: information capturing a transaction made between a person and a cultural organisation. This usually includes the type of purchase, what was purchased, the amount of the purchase, how it was purchased (e.g. online, at the counter);
- Person-related data: information describing personal attributes, including demographics (age, gender), identity (name, date of birth) and/or location (address, email address);
- Behavioural data: information available about behaviour in interaction with a cultural organisation. This can include self-disclosed feedback to programs, online behaviour, or observations obtained in physical settings;
- Biophysical data: information capturing signals about the body, including heart rate, temperature, movement, and related data.

1.2.2 Solid in EXCENTRIC

The plan for implementing Solid in EXCENTRIC is structured to develop the necessary core infrastructure and peripheral applications required for data sharing.

The project will initially set up a Solid Server based on the Solid Community Server⁸, which supports the Solid Protocol, account management, Pod functionality, and Linked Data (e.g. JSON-LD), for development and testing purposes. Organisations will be provided with a Solid Pod, which functions as the storage space for data resources accessed by agents (people or software). On the Solid platform, the project will develop data collection methods to import (existing) data from the pilot organisations to data Pods. While organisations will be given a Pod, the final hosting approach (whether on their own servers or through third-party providers) will be determined during subsequent workshops as described in software development planning in section 2 of this deliverable.

To facilitate organisational control over data and access, we will develop mechanisms for identity management (registration and log-in) and access management (authorisation and consent). The assumption in EXCENTRIC is that Solid Pods will be organisation-specific. Data sharing between organisations will therefore be at the application level based.

As a result of pre-piloting diagnostics and needs assessment (Deliverable 2.1), some pilots will develop **Solid-enabled data analytics tools** (peripheral components) that retrieve and use data stored in the Solid Pods to calculate and visualise specific pilot metrics⁹.

Figure 3: a depiction of the decentralised infrastructure where multiple organisations maintain their own Solid Pods. Furthermore, the figure demonstrates how a Solid-enabled analytical tools access standardised data from these Pods to calculate and visualise specific pilot metrics.

In summary, the table below describes summarises the core components of a Solid core data sharing architecture that EXCENTRIC will develop.

Solid component	Description
Solid Pod	The secure storage location for organizational data resources (peripheral component) and standard data models applicable to the pilot contexts (core component).
Client application	An application that manages the solid pod.
Authentication and authorization services	A service responsible for authenticating the agents and authorising data access (user or software).
Data Importer (API)	A service external data to be imported, standardised and transformed to the solid pod.

Table 1: Overview of the solid components needed for the pilot organisations to share data.

2. Methodology: Value-sensitive design

This section outlines a value-sensitive and agile design and development methodology for inter-organisational data sharing in EXCENTRIC.

Data intermediaries address multiple (possibly conflicting) values. How data intermediaries are assembled in practice influences what values are realised or constrained. To provide an example, data intermediaries frequently deal with questions of how to balance requirements of data protection and privacy and while ensuring data quality. Questions may arise around how much discretion data intermediaries provide to data owners regarding what data they want to share with other reusers.

In order to design a data sharing architecture, we therefore follow value-sensitive design (VSD). VSD is “an approach to the design of technology that accounts for human values in a principled and comprehensive manner throughout the design process” (Friedman and Hendry 2019). According to Friedman and Hendry (*ibid*), VSD “seeks to guide the shape of being with technology”. It is a transdisciplinary design framework that is aimed at “researchers, designers, engineers, policy makers, and anyone working at the intersection of technology and society [to provide] theory, method, and practice to account for human values in a principled systematic manner throughout the technical design process” (*ibid*).

To account for values in the design process of a data sharing architecture, VSD is usually organised in three phases: by means of conceptual, empirical, and technical investigations. As a transdisciplinary framework, VSD projects usually employ a range of research and design methods that are selected based on their suitability for a specific problem context (*ibid*). The same applies to the execution of different phases. Sometimes, conceptual investigations can lead the process while other times an empirical or technical investigation may be more suitable to frame the overall design process.

In the EXCENTRIC project, we conduct all three investigations and place particular emphasis on a mix between an empirical and technical investigation. Because we develop a novel technology that still requires design and responds to an operational challenge, we employ different qualitative social science and design methods to elicit salient values from cultural organisations regarding data sharing and data intense work practices. Our unit of analysis is therefore the technologies we develop for data analysis/reuse and data sharing, including the values it should manifest and the extent to which it aligns with the values of cultural organisations.

We use a broad concept of values to represent what is important to people in their lives. We extend the narrower definition of human values (values of ethical importance such as accountability, autonomy, human welfare or freedom from bias), often applied in VSD, to include various contextual values expressed in the context of designing data sharing architecture. (Le Dantec et al. 2009). By doing so, we follow design research which argues that people deem what is valuable in situ (Hauge 2018; Le Dantec et al. 2009) and through lived experiences. This point of view assumes that individual mental frames, the practical affordances of artifacts, and existing social institutions may influence what people deem important (ibid.). This view helps to understand how members of cultural organisations ground their value judgements (e.g. a personal mental frame, a social institution) when designing and using a technology. Additionally, we acknowledge that digital innovations must address multiple kinds of values beyond those pertaining to ethics, including industrial values (standardisation and efficiency), market-related values (competitiveness, profit), fame-related values (popularity), and/or domestic values (trust in a cultural institution). This broader understanding of the plural values that are mobilized through lived experiences enables us to articulate a broad set of design requirements for developing a data sharing architecture.

Below we explain the three investigations that EXCENTRIC will execute, after which we explain our process of gathering and interpreting data and integrating these into an agile development process.

2.1 Conceptual, empirical, and technical investigations

Conceptual investigations “comprise analytic, theoretical, or philosophically informed explorations of the central issues and constructs under investigation” (Friedman & Hendry, 2019). They are usually intended to address issues such as the identification of direct and indirect stakeholders of a specific design intervention, how the stakeholders are implicated, how one can define and systematize values, how to deal with possible value conflicts, and how to evaluate the successful application of VSD.

Within the EXCENTRIC project, we address each of these points as follows:

- We conduct a stakeholder mapping within pilot projects to understand who the relevant groups are that are affected by the pilot technology (see also D2.1).
- We provide an empirical systematisation of values, norms in the context of the technology, and design requirements, and how stakeholders understand these.
- We develop a methodology to identify value tensions in the process of designing and using technology.

- We develop a pilot testing methodology to assess pilot technology against the set of values that pilot partners wish to promote.

Empirical investigations can employ quantitative and qualitative social sciences methods to determine how social groups understand values within a certain design context, how they prioritise values, and how they experience technology to enable or constrain certain values, which can be based on quantitative and qualitative social sciences methods. This means that empirical investigations can be applied to understand values in specific contexts, to design prototypes or scenarios of use, and to evaluate the success of designs to support the realisation of intended values.

Within EXCENTRIC, we are focusing our empirical investigation on values that piloting organisations (and, if applicable, their networks) deem important in the context for the pilot project. This means that we are focusing on values within an organisation (both personal and organisational) that are relevant to take into consideration for the pilot design. Throughout the entire project, we apply different design-based and qualitative social scientific methods to elicit, analyse and systematize these values. We apply an iterative design process wherein the pilot technologies are gradually made more concrete, based on a documentation of salient values and design requirements (see also section 2.2.).

Our **technical investigation** takes the form of a proactive design of a data sharing architecture to support the values identified in the conceptual investigation. In the technical investigation we select, prioritise and operationalise values in order to translate them into code. Following our logic to develop an infrastructural core and peripheral elements, the technical investigation includes a systematic overview of values and their relevance for different technical components of our system. We pay special attention to technological “value levers” (Shilton 2013), that is, the core components of the data sharing architecture which influence how peripheral applications can operate and which can enforce certain values onto an entire ecosystem of reusers (e. g. through APIs, data models, data sharing request approval mechanisms).

2.2 Combining value-sensitive and agile design processes

The three phases of VSD are repeated iteratively in order “to inform and shape and reshape each other” (Friedman & Hendry, 2019). To structure this process, we combine agile methods with VSD (Umbrello and Gambelin 2023). The agile software development framework can be used to plan workflows, including the exploration of design requirements, scoping, and the development of software. An agile software development cycle usually includes the following steps: planning, design and development, as well as testing and evaluation. For each of these phases, we employ

different VSD methods, including value elicitation through prototyping, scenario methods, and value-oriented user testing.

We organise our conceptual, empirical, and technical investigations in four phases that map onto the software development cycle. In each phase, we use different methods that enable us to document different perspectives on the pilot technologies and envisaged data (sharing) practices. Each of these methods allows us to document different value statements and to define novel design requirements, or test alignment of our prototypes against these values. The phases are:

1. Preparation phase (prior to pilot design activities)
2. Identification of design requirements / planning phase
3. Development phase
4. Testing phase

In the first, preparation phase, we have conducted semi-structured interviews and workshops to discuss existing organisational practices, challenges, and plans for the pilot activities. These discussions have yielded information about the broader organisational context, processes and values within existing organisational contexts, as well as a first set of both moral and instrumental values that are related to the pilot project (see section 3). It is important to note that the pre-piloting interviews and workshops have yielded insights into more general organisational and personal values related to existing everyday work (see D 2.1), but not always specific to the pilot.

In the upcoming second phase, we will design prototypes of core infrastructure components (e. g. datasets to be shared, data sharing policies) as well as specific pilot applications (e. g. analytics apps for audience feedback). They serve as stimulus to elicit values from partner organisations regarding the technologies we develop. We will translate the values into design requirements (see conceptual investigation) and develop technological features based on these requirements in phase 3.

In the third, development phase, we develop the technological feature based on the requirements specified in phase 3. Based on monthly meetings with the pilot organisation, we monitor progress, discuss issues and refine features where needed.

In the fourth, testing phase, we will employ a set of test instructions to test the value-alignment of the data sharing architecture with pilot institutions and, if applicable, their networks. We will provide a set of data (sharing) practices to test the core data sharing architecture (e. g. data sharing mechanisms) and peripheral applications (such as analytics apps). Using a mix of a user survey and interviews, we gather evaluative statements on how the technology is perceived to promote the values relevant for the piloting institutions.

For planning purposes, we Table 2 provides an overview of the VSD methods per agile

development phase, articulating its activities and milestones. in Table 2, it should be acknowledged that these methods and the way they are ordered and phased will in practice overlap in practice and feed into one another, as is usual in iterative development.

Phase	Phase 1: pilot scoping (done)	Phase 2: Planning of design requirements	Phase 3: Development	Phase 4: User testing
Activities	Interviews & workshops to understand organisational problems and pilot activities	First prototype mock-up/wireframe; Value elicitation based on prototype; Value analysis/design requirements specification,	Development of first working prototype	Definition of user test instructions, user test execution/analysis, refinement of design requirements, adjustments of prototype)
Mile-stone	Pilot activity description	Design requirements specifications for core infrastructure and pilot projects	Working prototype aligned with value-based design requirements	Working prototype improved based on user test results

Table 2: Overview of VSD methods and agile development process.

2.2 Development Plans

The development plan will follow an agile, value-sensitive approach. We distinguish and define two types of development plans.

1. The first one is the development of the core Solid data sharing architecture that serves all pilots, focusing on authentication, authorisation, standardisation, data management, resource management and API's to import data.
2. The second one are pilot-specific development plan that focuses on data source identification, analytical tool development, and visualisation tools.

The final products by the end of phase 4 are:

1. A core Solid prototype platform deployable in 6 different pilots in the context of their scope as defined in D2.1.
2. Two analytical Solid-enabled tools to measure and monitor the intended focussed Social Return on Investment (SROI) for KBF and RE pilots.
3. A Solid-enabled data analytics tool to measure and monitor diversity for

informed programming for CTL as described in D2.1.

2.2.1 Core Solid data sharing architecture plan

Table 3 gives an overview of the Core Solid data sharing architecture development plan in 2026 for the essential services such as identity, access and storage management as well as standard data models and mechanisms for sharing data that are applicable for all pilots. The aim of the plan is to enable pilot organizations which ultimately will enable them to share data with their partners in relation to their specific pilot as described in 2.2.2.

Timeline 2026	Description of the core Solid data sharing architecture development activities	Result
Q1 (January - March): Architecture design requirements	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define value-sensitive co-creation workshop method to design requirement for core technologies; 2. Define initial standardised data models as needed per pilot for the categories: transaction, person-related, behaviour and biophysical data. 3. Define the Solid integration plan: Where data is stored (Pods), access model, and hosting strategy. 	O1. Standard data models; O2. Consent model O3. Hosting strategy
Q2-3 (April - September) Agile development & testing	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop data importer and API mechanism to collect and normalise pilot data into Pods. 2. Develop initial consent mechanism for sharing. 3. Develop granular access management. 4. Integrate analytical resources loyalty, focused SROI and diversity. 	O4. Functional pod management environment O5. Authentication server and access page (Register/Log-in) O6. Data import API for existing data in pilots O7. Consent management function in dashboard based on consent model
Q4 (Oct-Dec) Documentation and legacy planning	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Final review of core infrastructure stability, documentation of architecture. 2. Develop legacy planning. 	O8. Final core infrastructure source-code documentation for O1-O7.

Table 3: Overview of the core Solid architecture development plan applicable to all six pilots.

2.2.2. Pilot-Specific Development Plan

The pilot development focuses on developing specific Solid-enabled applications that integrate with the core infrastructure. Q2 and Q3 development phases will follow an agile, iterative sprint model with regular feedback sessions. In Table 4 below, we

present the pilot development activities, and explain which the technology development work that is being executed by pilot organisations and affiliated third-parties, and which the development tasks that are being conducted by Waag.

Pilot	Partner’s development scope (See D2.1 for more details)	Waag’s development scope
ATD	Simulation toolbox	Data sharing mechanism and data models for the toolbox.
Oulu2026	Master app	Data sharing mechanism and data models for the master App.
KBF/EFA	Dashboard for the integrated indicators for expanded network (still to be validated in Q1 2026).	Data sharing mechanism, data model to aggregate data for social outcome indicators and solid-enabled data analytics tool to visualise indicators.
CTL	Dashboard for planning of internal operational activities.	Data sharing mechanism and data model to aggregate data for diversity and solid-enabled data analytics tool to visualise indicators.
REF	Dashboard for measuring loyalty	Data sharing mechanism, data model to aggregate data for social outcome indicators and solid-enabled data analytics tool to visualise indicators.
CHM	Narrative game	Data sharing mechanism and data models for the narrative game.

Table 4: Development Scope between Partners and Waag

Table 5 provides a more detailed breakdown of Waag’s own development activities and the roles that Waag and pilot partners play in these activities. Co-creation activities that require involvement from partners are noted in brackets. When Waag is the sole organisation mentioned in brackets, this describes a development task that Waag executes based on partner feedback from the co-creation tasks. Table 5 does not reflect development work falling under the sole responsibility of the pilot partner.

Pilot	Q1 2026 Preparation & first prototype	Q2 and Q3 2026 Agile development and testing	Q4 2026 Documentation
ATD	1. Define the set of feasible input models (behavioural, physiological, etc.) (Waag/Dortmund). 2. Define standardised models for input data. 3. Define output data models and protocols (Waag/Dortmund)	1. Development of data models for both input and output data. (Waag/Dortmund) . 2. Integration in core Solid data sharing architecture and testing. (Waag/Dortmund).	Documentation of data models used in the toolbox. (Waag)

Oulu2026	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define sharing scope for venues contributing data to the Master App. (Waag/Oulu) 2. Developing data model for input data (sensors, traffic API) and output API layer. (Waag) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Integration in core Solid data sharing architecture and test sharing. (Waag/Oulu)* <p>* We prioritise the development for Oulu to early Q2 as the pilot has already started in January '26 and ends in December '26.</p>	Data model documentation (Waag)
KBF/EFA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define SROI scope and define a small set of social outcome indicators and data models. (Waag/EUR/KBF) 2. Define requirement dashboard to visualise SROI indicators and results. (Waag/EUR/KBF) 3. Design data analytics tool. (Waag) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop prototype Solid-enabled analytics tool for measuring and visualising social outcome indicators. (Waag) 2. Integration in core Solid prototype core data sharing architecture and test sharing. (Waag/KBF) 	Documentation of indicators and analytics tool. (Waag)
CTL	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define diversity data model using e.g., gender, ethnicity, artist demographics. (Waag /CTL). 2. Define the requirements data analytics tool and integration with CTL's platform. (Waag/EUR) 3. Design data analytics tool. (Waag) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop prototype Solid-enabled analytics tool for measuring and visualising diversity. (Waag) 2. Integration in core Solid platform and test sharing. (Waag/CTL) 	Documentation of data sources, diversity model and visualisation platform. (Waag)
ROMAE	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define SROI scope and define a small set of social outcome indicators and data models. (Waag /RE) 2. Define requirement data analytics tool to visualise SROI indicators and results and integration with REF's platform. (Waag /RE) 3. Design data analytics tool. (Waag) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop prototype Solid-enabled analytics tool to measure and visualise loyalty. (Waag) 2. Integration in core Solid data sharing architecture and test sharing. (Waag/RE) 	Documentation of data model, loyalty model and visualisation platform. (Waag)
CHM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define narrative prompts and click behaviours to collect qualitative experiential data. (Waag/CHM) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop a data model (fixed and variable layer) to support clustering visitors along criteria of similarity. (Waag) 	Documentation of data models. (Waag)

Table 5: Pilot specific development plan to be executed by Waag and with the contribution of pilot partners

3. Design requirements of the pilots

This section outlines the pilot activities which provide specific design contexts and problems, as well as the salient values that are relevant for this design context.

The conceptual heart of EXCENTRIC’s data sharing architecture are value-based design requirements. Values are usually not automatically translatable into technological designs. Rather, they have to be put in a form that can guide software developers in their development work.

There is a close relationship between values and software. Software is normative, because its affordances (Burgess et al. 2018) provide users with action frames that make certain behaviours more likely than others, however without fully determining it. Users can judge these affordances and opt to engage with certain software features or not and to comply with the norms embedded into software, or not (Scharlach and Hallinan 2023). Affordances describe what software enables users to do and they can therefore be documented as normative statements. For instance, a value such as privacy could be defined as “users are able to determine who can contact them via a messenger app”. Such a statement is very close to the definition of a user story and other formats used by software developers, while also providing a more nuanced idea of what a user understands privacy to be.

In EXCENTRIC, we are working towards documenting such normative statements which can specify the values of pilot organisations. We follow the work from van de Poel on the translation of values into design requirements (van de Poel 2013). He proposed a method to translate more abstract values into norms which he understands as definitions of values understood in the context of a specific technology. As described above, we develop normative statements that can be read as descriptions of a technology’s affordances: that is possible functions that the technology furnishes to users and which can be realized through user interaction with the technology.

Following van de Poel, we specify these norms further into design specifications for technological components of the data sharing architecture. The end-result is a long list of possible values and their norms that open up possibilities that developers can choose from. Below we provide a preliminary overview of values, norms, and design specifications for each pilot organizations based on the results in the deliverable 2.1 pre-piloting and needs assessment report. Following our iterative design process, this list is evolving throughout the design process.

Value	Norm (Definition of value, providing design requirement)	Design specification
Example:	Example:	Example:

Data ownership	Every audience member should have full control over all types of data they make accessible to others	Consent mechanism applies a granular permission model for data sharing
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Table 6: Example table that shows how values are translated into norms/design requirements and specifications

3.1. Fondazione Romaeuropa

As described in D2.1, the work with Fondazione Romaeuropa (ROMAE) will focus on developing a deeper and more coherent understanding of audience loyalty and the social value generated by the festival. Loyalty is understood not only as repeated attendance, but as a cultural and emotional relationship that reflects how audiences experience ROMAE and what the festival contributes to their lives. The scoping therefore emphasises relational, experiential, and qualitative dimensions alongside existing behavioural data.

To support this, the collaboration will draw on Social Return on Investment (SROI) and related value-assessment approaches, enabling ROMAE to articulate value through both quantitative indicators and narrative-based insights. Before the summer of 2026, the work will focus on defining a set of indicators, identifying key stakeholder groups, and specifying the qualitative and quantitative inputs needed to assess loyalty and social value in a holistic and repeatable way. This includes mapping current data sources, identifying gaps, and integrating more systematic forms of qualitative inquiry, such as targeted conversations with highly loyal audiences.

Value	Norm (Definition of value, providing design requirement)	Design specification
Diversity	Being able to attract novel segments of audiences, particularly young ones.	Data model: Data should enable one to segment audiences into groups, for instance based on age.
Loyalty	Being able to understand what influences the festival return rate of audiences.	Data model and data visualization tools in the dashboard: data should include information on influences of return rates.
Standardisation	Qualitative data should be documented and made accessible to other team members in a uniform fashion.	Qualitative data collection method and data access mechanisms: a uniform set of qualitative data (such as text-based feedback) and ways of making it accessible should be defined.

Table 7: Draft table of values, design requirements, and possible design specifications for ROMAE.

3.2. Computer History Museum

D2.1 defines the work with the Computer History Museum (CHM) that focuses on developing and testing a qualitative, ethics-conscious method for understanding audience tastes and interests through narrative interaction rather than conventional

demographic profiling. The core ambition is to move from transactional data (tickets, headcounts) to behavioural and value-oriented insights, capturing what people are drawn to, why they care, and how this can inform more resonant cultural programming. This aligns with CHM’s identity as an ethically driven “Artisanal Tech Lab”, where learning, responsibility and careful experimentation are central.

To operationalise this ambition, CHM is developing an interactive narrative game as a data collection and reflection tool. Through story-based choices and prompts, audiences will explore themes related to digital culture and computing, while the system records their paths, preferences and statements as “thick data”. This approach deliberately avoids intrusive data extraction and “data obesity”; instead, it privileges approximation and interpretive richness over precision. An initial version will be tested in real-world cultural contexts, including CHM’s own programme and external environments such as Ars Electronica, allowing the museum to observe how different audiences engage with the tool.

Value	Norm (Definition of value, providing design requirement)	Design specification
To be determined	To be determined	Data sharing policies: A shared set of policies has to be established that regulates the rights and responsibilities of organisations providing and reusing data.
Personal experience	Audience data should enable a CHM to understand a person’s motivation to go to an exhibition and what the person associates with “quality time” at the museum. The value of personal experience includes the ability to capture information about interactions between visitor and exposition that quantitative categories cannot capture.	Data capture tool: The capture tool can include open-ended forms of data collection (open questions) and feedback mechanisms.
Personal interests	Data should enable organisations to identify potentially interested groups by identifying overlaps between the offering of a cultural organisation/program and interests of a person. This value is motivated by the interest “to know what you don’t know” about a subset of the audience.	Data capture tool; data model: The data have to enable to match interests with individual audience members and/or groups of audiences.
Similarity	Data should enable to cluster (potential) audience members along criteria of similarity (e. g. taste profiles, common interests).	Data model: The data should enable grouping individual audience members along categories of similarity (e. g. similar taste).
Simplicity	Data entry should be as easy as possible for audience members so	Data capture tool: The capture tool may include a limited amount of simple direct

	that they do not feel overburdened. This value is connected to a value of efficiency of qualitative data collection (saving resources when gathering qualitative data).	questions or derive audience data from behavioural traces, without asking direct questions.
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Table 8: Draft table of values, design requirements, and possible design specifications for CHM

3.3. Cultural Trend Lisbon

As described in D2.1. the work with Cultural Trend Lisbon (CTL) will focus on turning diversity from a monitored value into a structurally embedded practice in programming and organisational decision-making. The main effort, led by Waag in collaboration with CTL, is to develop a dedicated analytical model that clarifies which types of diversity data are needed (e.g. gender, ethnicity, other relevant indicators), how they should be collected, and how they can be interpreted and used to inform programme choices over time. This includes moving from ad-hoc collection toward a repeatable, light-weight process that fits CTL’s existing workflows and capacities.

A key element of this work will be carried out together with at least one partner from CIRCUITO, enabling shared reflection on indicators, methods, and use of diversity data within a wider network of venues. This collaboration will support comparative perspectives, peer learning, and the gradual emergence of shared reference points for diversity monitoring across Portuguese cultural organisations. In parallel, CTL will continue developing its own internal programming and management tool with a third-party developer. The EXCENTRIC work will focus first on the analytical logic and data model; in a later phase, CTL will explore whether and how this diversity-analysis model can interface with the internal tool so that diversity data becomes a natural part of day-to-day processes rather than an occasional reporting exercise.

CTL’s strong relational culture and existing willingness to share knowledge, workflows, and aggregated insights, through networks such as CIRCUITO and Live Europe, position the organisation not only as a pilot site, but also as a contributor to capacity building around diversity monitoring in the wider cultural ecosystem. Over time, the aim is for CTL to operate with a clearer, more transparent and better-documented diversity practice, supported by simple governance and training steps that align with its values of accessibility, community, and shared responsibility.

Value	Norm (Definition of value, providing design requirement)	Design specification
Diversity	Being able to identify and group artists based on identity-related information, such as gender or ethnic background). This value is motivated by a desired to diversify	Data model and data analytics tool: The dataset and analytics should include identity-related variables that are associated to artists.

	programming.	
Standardisation (of organization-internal processes)	Being able to collect and use diversity related data in a standard fashion.	Data capture tool, data model, and analytics tool: (Diversity) data should use a common set of categories, including by gathering data that uses common categories and formats.
Interoperability (with an external network)	Diversity data should be understandable and usable by a wider network of organisations, including through technical interoperability (using standard data models) and semantic interoperability (using data models that reflect the knowledge needs within the network)	Data model: The dataset should be structured to include categories that are relevant and usable across organisations.

Table 9: Draft table of values, design requirements, and possible design specifications for CTL.

3.4. Dortmund Theatre

The Academy for Theatre and Digitality Dortmund (ATD) as described in D2.1 is a distinct type of EXCENTRIC pilot: it is not audience-facing or commercially oriented, but operates as an R&D laboratory dedicated to dramaturgical and technological innovation. Its work focuses on developing a toolbox capable of translating live audience input into musical or performative parameters, producing a value-added artistic tool for its sister organisation, the Dortmund Philharmonic Orchestra (DPO).

Within this pilot, data functions as a performative material rather than as a resource for audience analytics. Most data are collected only temporarily during rehearsals or performances, processed immediately through algorithms, and then discarded or retained only in aggregated, non-identifiable form. The system does not track individuals but interprets the audience as a collective signal whose fluctuations shape the artistic output. This makes the pilot a valuable test case for privacy-aware, non-extractive data use in the performing arts, requiring nuanced consent mechanisms, clear communication, and robust standardisation methods for input data.

Value	Norm (Definition of value, providing design requirement)	Design specification
Privacy	Data should be aggregated in such a way that personally identifiable information cannot be deduced from a dataset.	Data model and anonymisation functionalities The role of consent and user control over data is still to be discussed.
Reusability (of audience-related data)	Third-parties should be able to use audience-related data. <i>Note: While this value is still under-</i>	Data model and data access mechanisms.

	<i>specified, it may include other values such as openness (reuse for different purposes), standardisation (uniform data definitions), and other values that describe enabling means of reusability, or goals for reusability.</i>	
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Table 10: Draft table of values, design requirements, and possible design specifications for ATD.

3.5. European Festival Association / Krakow KBF

Within the EXCENTRIC pilot as described in D2.1, the proposed way forward for KBF is to implement a focused and practical Social Return on Investment (SROI) approach, adapted to the organisation’s scale, existing datasets, and strategic needs. Rather than building a complete SROI framework, which would exceed the scope of this project, the pilot will concentrate on a small number of high-value outcomes that meaningfully capture the festival’s social contribution and support evidence-based curation. These outcomes may relate to local well-being, community engagement, volunteer experience, youth or NEET¹⁰ participation, and the inclusion of migrant communities.

To define these outcomes, KBF will take part in a dedicated workshop to:

- identify the most relevant social impact domains for the festival
- map existing data sources across departments (including the Observatory for Cultural Trends)
- determine where minimal additional data collection may be required.

Value	Norm (Definition of value, providing a design requirement)	Design specification
Social value	Being able to understand and make visible social benefits of festival activities in datasets. <i>(Note: this value reflects the broader goal to increase SROI and needs to be disaggregated further other kinds of values in future design iterations)</i>	Data model and data analytics tool: to be determined
Understandability	Being able to understand and interpret festival data within one organisation as well as across organisations.	Data model and data analytics tool: to be determined
Reusability of analytical tools and data	Other festival networks should be able to reuse tools to monitor social outcome indicators. <i>Note: while this value is still under-specified, it may include other values such as openness (reuse for different purposes), standardisation (uniform data definitions), and other values that describe enabling</i>	Data model and data access mechanisms: to be determined

	<i>means of reusability, or goals for reusability.</i>	
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Table 11: Draft table of values, design requirements, and possible design specifications for KBF.

3.6. Oulu Culture Foundation

The Oulu2026 pilot as defined in D2.1, will address its operational challenge by developing a unified Venue Master App, a centralised operational environment that brings together currently fragmented datasets across the city’s cultural ecosystem. By integrating information from IoT sensors, ticketing and access systems, mobility and weather APIs, staffing tools, and qualitative insights from cultural operators, the platform will provide real-time situational awareness and support informed, proactive decision-making during the ECOC year. This shared operational overview aims to reduce the burden on individual venue managers, strengthen coordination across more than 100 partner organisations, and ensure a smooth and safe visitor experience during periods of peak activity.

Beyond the technical architecture, the pilot will establish the organisational and governance structures required for responsible data sharing, ethical use, and long-term maintenance of the system. Because Oulu2026 functions as a temporary, start-up-like organisation, defining clear responsibilities, documentation practices and sustainable ownership models is essential to ensure that the digital infrastructure continues to serve the city after 2026. Accessibility and usability will remain key priorities, ensuring that staff with varied digital skills can navigate the system confidently and effectively.

The next phase of the pilot will focus on:

- Refining the data architecture, identifying the most critical inputs for operational decision-making.
- Co-designing user workflows with venue teams and cultural operators to ensure high usability and relevance.
- Testing governance models for data roles, security, permissions and long-term stewardship.
- Piloting early prototypes in selected venues, iterating based on real-world feedback from front-line staff.
- Preparing a sustainability and legacy plan that defines who will maintain, evolve and benefit from the platform beyond 2026.

Value	Norm (Definition of value, providing design requirement)	Design specification
Accessibility of the	Information should be easy to understand and navigate for diverse	Graphical user interface (GUI) has to comply with recognised accessibility

data tools	users.	standards.
Openness (of source code and data)	Data and information should be open to other venues and cultural organisations.	Data access mechanisms: data should be accessible in machine-readable form and licensed under an open licence. Source code should be openly accessible in a software repository (e. g. Gitlab)

Table 12: Draft table of values, design requirements, and possible design specifications for Oulu 2026.

4. Conclusion

Throughout the first year, we gained insights from online interviews, on-site workshops, and digital maturity assessments (see also D2.1 and D2.3). Based on this, we have established the socio-technical development plan in alignment with the values of the pilots and EXCENTRIC's goals.

Our proposed architectural framework distinguishes between an **infrastructural core**, responsible for identity, access management, and standardisation and **peripheral applications** tailored to the specific needs of the six pilots such indicators. Using Solid protocol allows pilots to have control over their data while ensuring interoperability for scalability and future expansions.

The Design Requirements section remains a living document This status reflects the iterative nature of VSD, as the values and norms regarding data sharing will continue to be refined and documented during the co-creation workshops planned for Q1 2026.

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